

The Dominican Teachers as Quintessential Persona in an ASEAN-oriented college

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Abstract

Teachers should receive adequate financial remuneration and other non-monetary benefits commensurate to their professional expertise and services, in order to stay and enjoy life in the academe. Other than the teaching profession, the corporate world is in a place where people are competent and qualified like teachers but well-remunerated. Teachers do not experience the same set up, not even at SDCA. The descriptive-correlational design was used, and data were gathered from the 435 respondents consisted of the Deans, Program Chairpersons, Teachers, and Students using an adapted questionnaire survey from the Education International Research Institute (2015) based in Brussels, Belgium. The simple random sampling was utilized to determine the sample size of the student-respondents, while the rest of the respondent-groups had population size. A T-test of significant difference was used between two groups or two points in time means that there is a measurable difference between the groups and that, statistically, the probability of obtaining that difference is very small. The Allport's Three Level Traits Theory provided the theoretical framework for this study.

The findings of the study revealed that the occupational status and professional image of Dominican Teachers were average, as perceived by the four-group of respondents, while, characters Traits were high. They have possessed the cardinal traits as quintessential persona reflective of the theory of Dr. Gordon Williard Allport of Harvard University in a ASEAN-oriented college following "the quality assurance processes that underpin the ASEAN Qualifications Reference Framework; foster the use of quality assurance frameworks as a benchmark; and to enable support for lifelong learning" (AQRFGS, 2014). Hence, there is no significant difference between the perceptions of Teachers, and Deans; Teachers and Program Chairs, except on the perceptions of Teachers vis-à-vis with the students on the occupational status and professional image of teachers. Finally, it appears that the perceptions of the four-respondent group differed, but the data supported a novel idea that the disagreement is a way of presenting a new outlook for the teachers. What teachers of SDCA should be, rather than what are they or who are they, though majority of the respondents expressed not statistically significant. It can be further deduced that while teachers considered their occupational status and professional image as "average" the students perceived it the opposite way.

Keywords: Dominican Teachers. Quintessential. Persona. ASEAN Framework. Status. Image. Traits.

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Introduction

Teachers are quintessential (representing the most perfect or typical example, Concise Oxford English Dictionary, 2008) persona because they are not only the dispensers of knowledge but leaders, who lead their students to reach greater heights of life. They constitute the bedrock of Philippine Education for national growth and development. The level of growth that a nation can attain is measured by the kind of the citizens it has produced through the various technical training and disciplinal areas that colleges and universities provide to their students who constitute the citizenry of a nation. In the process of human development, the teachers compose the cadre of highly trained specialists in various academic disciplines. They are responsible in the delivery of the tri-focal functions of higher education of which, teaching is their prime duty.

The teachers are the greatest human resources of an institution of higher learning. They are regarded as scientists and artists whose preeminent responsibility is to mold students to become responsible, productive and law-abiding citizens in school and in society. Notwithstanding the foremost moral obligation of the parents to nurture their children as well. In the engagement of their scientific, intellectual, and practical activities, they take various roles as thespian, mentor, guidance counselor, social worker, or a prime mover in the construction and reconstruction of human development. They need to be economically upright. While adequate financial remuneration is not the only index of teachers' happiness, but it is by far a motivator as they immerse with the stakeholders in the workplace and achieve moral ascendancy. "As teachers are a fundamental condition for guaranteeing quality education, teachers and educators should be empowered, adequately recruited and remunerated, motivated, professionally qualified, and supported within well-resourced, efficient and effectively governed systems (Education 2030 Framework for Action).

Hence, this study examined the occupational status, professional image, and character traits of Dominican teachers in an ASEAN-oriented college. Towards this direction, policy measures will be crafted and institutionalized for the professional advancement of teachers in the teaching service that may affect student achievements; the stature of St. Dominic College of Asia; and the difference they have made in the past and will further make in years ahead.

Methodology

This study utilized the descriptive-correlational design. Descriptive study is the best method to describe the data and characteristics about what is being studied because it describes, explains, and validates findings. Description entails following creative exploration and serves to organize the findings in order to fit them with explanations, and then test or validate those explanations (Bickman and Rog, 1998). And, correlational studies are primarily designed to investigate whether there is a relationship between two or more variables (Kumar, 2011). There were 435 respondents consisting of three categories: Deans (2), Program Chairpersons (15), Teachers (84), and Students (334). The first three respondent-groups constituted the population size, while the students' group as sample size. An adapted questionnaire survey from the Education International Research Institute (2015) based in Brussels, Belgium. Adapted in the sense that some parts of the original instrument were modified/revised to make them suitable for a new use or purpose in the context of SDCA. The survey instrument had a consistency index of 0.80 based on Cronbach's alpha Coefficient of Reliability (Introduction to SAS, 2016). An informed consent was sought from the respondents and ethical review was done by the Research Ethics Committee of SDCA in a meeting called for the purpose.

The presentation, interpretation, and analysis of data using the appropriate statistical tools were adequately done reflecting the theory adopted and the related literature cited. The Frequency count and percentage were applied to any variable that is measured on any one of the four measurement scales. It groups respondents into the sub-categories in which a variable has been measured or coded (Kumar, 2011, p. 386). T-test of significant difference was used to determine a difference between two groups is unlikely to have occurred because the sample happened to be a typical (www.stat.yale.edu).

Results and Discussion

Occupational Status, Professional Image, and Character Traits of Dominican Teachers were discussed as main variables of the study

Table 1.1 Level of Occupational Status of Teachers at SDCA

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Perceived Occupational Status	84	1.00	3.78	1.4785	.63013
Valid N (listwise)	84				

The teachers at SDCA perceived themselves as average in occupational status (is the amount of esteem attributed to members of a profession by a culture, Nugent, 2013) as reflected by 1.48 mean rating and a standard deviation of .63. This relates with a study in Europe, of which the general perception of teachers' occupational status is seen as average in all education sectors except for higher education. Lower status is recorded more often for early childhood and vocational education and for education support staff. Over half of the respondents reported a decline in teacher status over the last 10 years (Education International, 2015).

While the teachers in higher education received high esteem from the public in Europe, but not in the Philippines because "teachers and education workers are underpaid and overworked in general," specifically at SDCA of which the present study is under consideration. Teachers' positive sense of their status is closely linked to other aspects of quality education, including continuous professional development, engagement in research, collaboration and exchange with other teachers, and involvement in decision-making (Hargreaves and Flutter, 2013).

Table 1.2 Level of Professional Image of Teachers at SDCA

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Perceived Professional Image	84	1.00	3.60	1.5012	.59100
Valid N (listwise)	84				

The professional image (is a set of qualities and characteristics that represent perceptions of your competence and character as judged by both influencers and peers, Nattziger, 2011) of teachers at SDCA as perceived by themselves as average with the mean of 1.50 and a standard deviation of .59. This finding has reinforced a large-scale global research study of MacBeath (2012) which has shown that wherever teachers have been asked about their priorities and satisfiers, in South Africa, Sub-Saharan Africa, Europe, or North America, they refer to the importance of recognition and respect for their daily challenges. These common factors, essential for all teachers, shape the status of the teaching profession and play a crucial role in delivering quality and ensuring equity in education. On the contrary, in countries where the teaching profession is highly valued in society, such as Finland, Singapore, and South Korea, students seem to learn more effectively (Burns and Darling-Hammond, 2014). Regardless of their present circumstances, the professional image of teachers at SDCA and abroad has become the warp and woof of their existence and motivation to work harder for the well-being of the profession and of their students under their stewardship.

Table 1.3 Level of Character Traits of Teachers at SDCA

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Perceived Character Traits	84	2.30	4.70	3.4607	.49771
Valid N (listwise)	84				

The perceived Character Traits (refer to the 3 traits like Cardinal, Central, and Secondary that dominate and shape the person's behavior in life, Allport, 1936) of SDCA's faculty members is high as perceived by the teachers themselves with the mean rating of 3.4. The findings reveal positive underpinning that faculty members of St. Dominic College of Asia fall under the Central Traits (These are the general characteristics that form the basic foundations of personality. These central traits, while not as dominating as cardinal traits, are the major characteristics you might use to describe another person, terms such as intelligent, honest, shy and anxious are considered central traits (Allport, 1936, p. 2). The respondents claimed that they have been passionate and visionary in the delivery of quality instruction; rare of their own right; honest and sincere in the exercise of their profession; intelligent and anxious of their employment conditions and career prospects. Just like most of the career persons, they have their likes and dislikes. They care for their students as surrogate children. And in social dimension of their lives, they are sociable, optimistic, and crave for change and excitement in both public and private lives. Most of all, they are reserve, reliable, optimistic in their profession, indeed, quintessential persona in the academe.

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Perceived Occupational Status	351	1.00	4.00	1.7279	.67797
Valid N (listwise)	351				

The deans, program chairpersons and students perceived the occupational status of teachers as average. This is reflected with the mean of 1.73 and a standard deviation of .68. This finding corroborates with the study of (Cohen & Cohen, 2003) which reported that in spite of doing various responsibilities, their immeasurable and unparalleled commitment in the service, in the end, teachers have not gained high prestige which had been given to corporate employees/officials, politicians, movie stars, and singers, businessmen, and other artists/professionals from other fields of life. In addition, countries which become more Western in their orientation, in their economies, and in their outlook and values, the prestige of the teaching profession decreases. In America, teachers often get a bum rap – from parents, school administrators and even politicians when the profession is a beleaguered one: teachers are overworked, underpaid and underappreciated. But what about teachers in other countries? Is this solely an American problem? Or do teachers around the world suffer from the same lack of respect? (Falla, 2013).

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Perceived Professional Image	351	1.00	4.00	1.7991	.67054
Valid N (listwise)	351				

The deans, program chairpersons and students perceived the professional image of teachers as average. This finding is aligned with a study, in Brazil, of which society recognizes the social role of the teacher, more than that of the support staff, but the salaries and working conditions discourage young people to go into the profession. Corollary, in Kenya, Uganda, Japan, United Kingdom, Liberia, United States of America, Netherlands and Australia of which the public perception on the teaching profession is low or not that much compared to other professions of the same qualification; salary is much lower compared to other professions either in private and public sectors and the young people are not interested to enter the teaching profession (UNESCO, 2000). Despite the dismal picture of the teachers' professional image, they have remained faithful in the teaching service at St. Dominic College of Asia. Sarafoglu (1997) also found intrinsic reasons why teachers stay in the profession. These reasons include a love of learning, a love of children, resilience, collegiality, and reflectivity.

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Perceived Character Traits	351	1.50	5.00	3.5942	.65333
Valid N (listwise)	351				

The deans, program chairpersons and students perceived the character traits of teachers as high. This perception supports the prior findings in Table 1.3 of which the teachers have high perception on their character traits. Interestingly, teachers with good character traits have strong influence towards the character formation of their students. Teaching is a profession that lies at the heart of both the learning of children and young people and their social, cultural and economic development. It is crucial to transmitting and implanting social values, such as democracy, equality, tolerance, cultural understanding and respect for each person's fundamental freedoms (Education International, 2011, Article 29).

Table 3.1 Significant Difference between the Assessment of Teachers and Deans on the Occupational Status of Teachers at SDCA

	N	T-test comput- ed	P value	Inter- preta- tion	Decision
Perceived Occu- pational Status	435	-.003	.998	Not Signifi- cant	Cannot Reject Ho
Valid N (listwise)	435				

There is no significant difference between the assessment of teachers and deans on the occupational status of teachers. As shown in the T-test computed value of -.003 and P value of .998 which are higher than the Alpha level of 0.05. The advanced null hypothesis cannot be rejected. Hence, the perceptions of deans vis-à-vis with the teachers on their occupational status are the same as earlier shown in Tables 1.1 and 2.1. as average respectively. Symeonidis V. et al (2015) reported and concluded in a global study that, the general perception of teachers' occupational status is seen as average in all education sectors with the exception of higher education. On the contrary, the occupational status of SDCA's teachers is just average as perceived by the 3-respondent group and the teachers themselves.

Table 3.2 Significant Difference between the Assessment of Teachers and Deans on the Professional Image of Teachers at SDCA

	N	T-test comput- ed	P value	Inter- preta- tion	Decision
Perceived Profes- sional Image	435	-.442	.660	Not Signifi- cant	Cannot Reject Ho
Valid N (listwise)	435				

There is no significant difference between the assessment of teachers and deans on the professional image of teachers as attested by the T-test computed value of -.442 and P value of .660 which are higher than the Alpha level of 0.05. The advanced null hypothesis cannot be rejected. Hence, the perceptions of deans vis-à-vis with the teachers on their professional image are the same as shown in Table 1.2 and 2.2 as average respectively. The results relate with the Lucman's study (2015) that the professional self-image of teachers in the Philippines is inconsistent with their perceived occupational prestige. Because society considers their occupation as inferior to other professions, teachers tend to experience affective problems including various forms of anxiety and an exaggerated sense of pride. To address these problems, they employ at least five agency-based strategies namely, self-reflection, performance improvement, academic advancement, professional development, and awareness.

Table 3.3 Significant Difference between the Assessment of Teachers and Deans on the Character Traits of Teachers at SDCA

	N	T-test comput- ed	P value	Inter- preta- tion	Decision
Perceived Character Traits	435	1.212	.229	Not Signifi- cant	Cannot Reject Ho
Valid N (listwise)	435				

There is no significant difference between the assessment of teachers and deans on the character traits of teachers as expressed in T-test computed value of 1.212 and P value of .229 which are higher than the Alpha level of 0.05. This is reinforced by the earlier findings in Tables 1.3 and 2.3 as high respectively. It is important to mention that 'good teaching' and 'poor teaching' have been interchanged and operationalized with 'good teacher' and 'poor teacher' from time to time in researches since the ideas and actions happen in an environment in which teachers function and therefore, the character of the environment is dependent on the personality of the teacher (Leinhardt, 1988). Good teachers are surrounded by human qualities of understanding, self-assurance, regard for others, empathy, fair play, appreciation, adaptability, objectivity, interest, friendliness, maturity, credibility, trustworthiness, humor, polished delivery and ability to engage which allows them to influence students (Beishuzen, Hof, Putten, Bouwmeester, & Asscher, 2001; Chickering & Gamson, 1991).

4.1 Significant Difference between the Assessment of Teachers and Program Chairs on the Teachers' Occupational Status

	N	T-test comput- ed	P value	Inter- preta- tion	Decision
Perceived Occu- pational Status	435	.034	.973	Not Signifi- cant	Cannot Reject Ho
Valid N (listwise)	435				

There is no significant difference between the assessment of teachers and program chairs on the occupational status of teachers as shown in T-test computed value of -.034 and P value of .973 which are higher than the Alpha level of 0.05. The perceptions of program chairs vis-à-vis with teachers on their occupational status are the same. According to Lin Chi'ing-Jiang (1994), two variables are related to the identities of teachers are worth studying, namely, occupational prestige and professional self-image. The occupational prestige of teachers refers to the prestige ranking of teachers' work by different members of society engage in different occupation. This may not represent teachers' actual status but is nevertheless a good indicator of it (Chi'ing-Jiang, 1994).

The ranking of teachers' prestige by different members of society reflects society's general concept of the value of teachers' work. Teachers themselves would almost constantly compare their profession with others to assess their social status (Chistolini, 2010). Here, social status is understood as "the position of an individual or a social group in the social stratification on a scale of social prestige" (Aelterman, Rots, & Sabbe, 2002). The position in this social hierarchy is determined by factors such as salary, responsibility, social benefit and social influence (Aelterman et al, 2002). Perception of the social status of teachers, meanwhile, is partly influenced by the public opinion formulated about their profession, e.g. in the media (Aelterman et. al, 2002).

4.2 Significant Difference between the Assessment of Teachers and Program Chairs on Teachers' Professional Image

	N	T-test computed	P value	Interpretation	Decision
Perceived Professional Image	435	-.285	.776	Not Significant	Cannot Reject Ho
Valid N (listwise)	435				

There is no significant difference between the assessment of teachers and program chairs on the professional image of teachers as attested by the T-test computed value of -.285 and P value of .776 which are higher than the Alpha level of 0.05. Hence, the perceptions of teachers vis-à-vis with the program chairs on their professional image are the same. As argued by Chi'img-Jiang (1994), "Cross-cultural studies indicate that the occupational prestige and professional self-image of teachers vary widely across the world. For instance, in Taiwan, despite the popular notion that the social status and prestige of teachers have significantly declined, it was found that most teachers in Taiwan are still highly respected and honored. The same could not be said for countries such as Italy, Cyprus, and Libya. However, in an international survey conducted by Chistolini (2010), she found that in these countries, society is less appreciative of the contribution teachers make. Teachers in Poland, meanwhile, expressed their desire to see an improvement in the way they are perceived. This feeling may imply that they themselves perceive their ranking in society as unsatisfactory, thus in need of enhancement. In another study, it was shown that higher status and self-image proved elusive for most Belgian teachers (Depaepe & Simon, 1997). In sum, the previous findings are reinforced by the findings of this present study that teachers' professional image has remained as average.

4.3 Significant Difference between the Assessment of Teachers and Program Chairs on Teachers' Character Traits

	N	T-test computed	P value	Interpretation	Decision
Perceived Character Traits	435	.523	.602	Not Significant	Cannot Reject Ho
Valid N (listwise)	435				

There is no significant difference between the assessment of teachers and program chairs on the occupational status of teachers as shown in T-test computed value of .523 and P value of .602 which are higher than the Alpha level of 0.05. Hence, the perceptions of program chairs vis-à-vis with the teachers on their character traits are the same, as high. Distinct of their traits lead them to walk through their profession because, teaching is one of the hardest jobs there is. The secret that keeps them going is that great teachers really, really want to be great teachers, and they'll stop at nothing to succeed. A great teacher will do almost anything to help their students. They always make time and they're always willing to help. If something doesn't work, they'll work tirelessly until they find a solution. A teacher's work is never done but the best ones never stop trying, they never quit (Meer, 2018).

5.1 Significant Difference between the Assessment of Teachers and Students on Teachers' Occupational Status

	N	T-test computed	P value	Interpretation	Decision
Perceived Academic Status	435	3.892	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Valid N (listwise)	435				

There is a significant difference between the assessment of teachers and students on the occupational status of teachers as expressed in the T-test computed value of 3.892 and P value of .000 which is lower than the Alpha level of 0.05. As earlier discussed, the teacher-respondents rated their occupational status as average, but the students perceived it otherwise because as they interact on a daily basis, students must have observed that majority of their teachers at SDCA have good occupational status, although a few may have better economic condition brought about by additional income through business ventures aside from their employment at SDCA. So, a better occupational status of teachers leads to positive public image and elated social status for teachers. It has been observed that teachers of good economic condition or much more economically affluent in life have strong influence on their students who most likely follow the career path of their teachers and eventually becomes teachers in the future.

5.2 Significant Difference between the Assessment of Teachers and Students on Teachers' Professional Image

	N	T-test comput- ed	P value	Inter- preta- tion	Decision
Perceived Profes- sional Image	435	3.226	.001	Signifi- cant	Reject Ho
Valid N (listwise)	435				

There is a significant difference between the assessment of teachers and students on the professional image of teachers as shown in T-test computed value of 3.226 and P value of .001 which is lower than the Alpha level of 0.05. The same findings can be perused in Tables 1.2, 2.2, 3.2, and 4.2. As it is, there is a felt-need to raise the professional image of teachers, as argued by Jónasson (2014) "the professional identity and ethos of teachers as a professional group are empowered with new knowledge, good arguments and a vocabulary to continuously define or redefine the character and agenda of their profession. Politicians and the general public will also benefit from explanations on why the teachers and schools must be provided with good working conditions and be fully trusted as professionals to engage in their tasks. I will mention three parts of the proposed Manifesto that I think are both very important but also sufficiently complex as to merit special attention. These concern the aims of education and how these need to reflect the challenges of a rapidly changing global society, the challenges to teachers as professionals and finally the actions that are needed, collectively and individually, in order to ensure the necessary development of education."

5.3 Significant Difference between the Assessment of Teachers and Students on Teachers' Character Traits

	N	T-test comput- ed	P value	Inter- preta- tion	Decision
Perceived Profes- sional Image	435	1.745	.082	Not signi- fi- cant	Cannot Re- ject Ho
Valid N (listwise)	435				

There is no significant difference between the assessment of teachers and students on the character traits of teachers as presented in the T-test computed value of 1.745 and P value of .082 which are higher than the Alpha level of 0.05. Hence, the perceptions of the two groups are one and the same. Along that line, Wale (2019) has this to say, "Much of what students learn from their greatest teachers is not detailed on a syllabus. Teachers who help us grow as people are responsible for imparting some of life's most important lessons. During their initial school years, students encounter, perhaps for the first time, other children of the same age and begin to form some of their first friendships.

As a teacher, you will show your students how to become independent and form their own relationships, you will carefully guide them and intervene when necessary. School is as much a place of social learning as academic learning, and this is true, not only in our early years of education, but all the way through college. Armed with a supportive and well-educated administration, there is no limit to the influence a teacher can have on one, or many, students' lives. Though a teacher's influence on the social sphere of school lessens as students mature, those early lessons still have an effect on how they will interact with others in the future. Teachers are founts of experience. They have already been where their students are going, undergone what they will go through and are in a position to pass along lessons, not only regarding subject matter, but lessons on life."

Conclusion and Recommendation

The occupational status and professional image of Dominican Teachers are average, similar with the global standing among the 79 respondent-countries except in few countries which regarded teaching as highly respected profession. Hence, the teacher-respondents perceived themselves as passionate, visionary, with sense of anxiety, excitement, and temper in the performance of their professional career. Further studies should be conducted in other private and public colleges and universities in the Philippines to validate the findings of the study which will include variables other than mentioned in this study. The professional development framework may be designed to improve the professional status and professional image of the teachers which are at stake as of the present.

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